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Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable describes the outcomes of the task T6.1 of the AgeingAtWork project, focusing on the development of a tool aimed at enhancing situational awareness of ageing workers through augmented reality displays. In our scope, we have aimed at providing the ageing worker, through AR glasses or also through their mobile device, with projections that visually describe significant parameters of the device and task at hand, providing guidelines through situations that can both refer to life-long training sessions or the daily job. The projections aim to support the ageing workers into reducing the mental load, enabling them to better focus on the crucial aspects of their task.

In this direction, this deliverable describes the developed Augmented Reality (AR-based situational) tools for worker awareness enhancement, which allows visualizing scenarios to the final user, through a scenarios definition that can include a series of steps and instructions therein, in relation to machines used in the worker's site. Following this, the deliverable presents two core use cases that have been implemented in the scope of the project, within the functional prototype of the AR Viewing Tool. The tool has been developed as a set of software applications (VR and AR Clients) that can support a wide range of physical devices (mobile, AR glasses, etc.) enabling an immersive framework for the visualization of training, enhancing the worker's context awareness while using a new device. The scenarios (step wizard form), enhance the worker's context awareness while using a new device, as is seen through the use cases which highlight the value of our prototype system

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
HMD	Head Mounted Display
GPS	Global Positioning System
HAR	Human Activity Recognition
XML	Extensible Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
POI	Points of Interest
SDK	Software Development Kit

Table 1. Definitions

1 Introduction

Augmented Reality (AR) is an emerging technology that enhances our perception of the real world by overlaying virtual information on top of it. According to Azuma [1] an AR system must combine real and virtual content, be interactive in real time and be registered in 3D. As part of the Ageing@Work platform, a Situation Awareness tool has been developed, which is based on AR techniques and enables the user to gain better real-time feedback from the environment through localized indicators, as well as be trained in various scenarios relevant to their field of work. For workspace awareness, people need to gather information from the environment, understand it and predict what this means for the future [2]. Offering an immersive environment, AR can contribute to this by allowing the user to observe the environment in greater detail, and process a greater amount of stimuli. In addition, the immersion provided by AR-based systems has shown to significantly reduce training time and costs required by employers [3]. As such, AR technologies can be particularly helpful while considering ageing workers, as they can offer them with respectively enhanced situation awareness while operating or learning to operate a new device in their workspace.

The Situation Awareness Tool presented herein comprises two main elements: The AR Viewing tool and the AR Scenario Creation tool. The Scenario Creation tool lets users author their own training scenarios, using an expressive and intuitive node-based interface, and make those available for viewing and training. The Viewing tool is the counterpart of the Authoring tool that actually enables the immersive viewing of and interaction with the generated training scenarios.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

The Situation Awareness Tool presented herein comprises two main elements: The AR Viewing tool and the AR Scenario Creation tool. The Scenario Creation tool lets users author their own training scenarios, using an expressive and intuitive node-based interface, and make those available for viewing and training. The Viewing tool is the counterpart of the Authoring tool that actually enables the immersive viewing of and interaction with the generated training scenarios.

This deliverable summarizes the AR Situation Awareness tool, and its main components, namely the AR Viewing tool and the AR Authoring tool. A short outline of the tools is provided, and their actual use in case studies is then presented.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

As part of Ageing@Work, several tools are being developed that spearhead the use of AR in diverse training and collaboration scenarios. These tools aim to contribute to the lifelong training paradigm [4] and to knowledge management within an Ageing@Work-enabled organization. In particular, the present deliverable is related to D6.3 “AR-based Telepresence Tool for Remote Collaboration”; the tools outlined in both deliverables make use

of related technologies in order to achieve different goals. While in the case of the present deliverable the goal is the development of an on-site Situation Awareness enhancement Tool, in the case of D6.3, the aim is to outline the development of a tool for Remote Collaboration.

The Situation Awareness tool outlined herein has as a target audience the workers occupied at an organization, which aim to constantly improve their knowledge on relevant procedures within the organization. In particular, two discrete groups are considered: Senior workers with extensive experience and knowledge, who may participate by generating training scenarios, thereby translating their tacit knowledge into well-formulated training material; and young workers with limited as of yet experience who may participate by following training material, thereby improving their knowledge and experience.

Considering the overall architecture of Ageing@Work, Figure 1 presents the relationship of the Situation Awareness tools outlined in this deliverable, with the rest of the project architecture. In particular, it is seen that the primary relationship is with the Ageing@Work Mobile App and with the Ageing@Work Centralized repository, where the tool gathers and stores the generated knowledge.

Figure 1 Ageing@Work Architecture, highlighting the position of the overall Productivity Enhancement Tools of WP⁶, and specifically the Situational Awareness Tool described in the present deliverable

2 AR Situation Awareness Tool

As mentioned in the introduction, the AR Situation Awareness tool comprises two major components, namely the AR Viewing Tool and the AR Authoring tool. The AR Viewing Tool is an application to navigate training scenarios, enabling the workers to be trained on various procedures in a safe and intuitive environment, that allows gaining the necessary information while minimizing issues such as equipment failures, and injuries, and ensuring a better comprehension of knowledge. The tool has the capability of navigating the procedure step by step, following sequences, loops, and conditions included in the procedure and, in doing this, it delivers the content which has been previously managed and included as resource by the Authoring Tool. The content delivered could depend both on the capabilities of the platform (for example, the operator will be exposed to video, sound, images, 3D models etc. depending on the fact that h/w platform can render that kind of content).

Furthermore, the operator has the opportunity to choose the best content that fits its own needs among the contents that can be deployed and delivered in the platform he/she is actually using. The tool has been developed in Unity, using the Vuforia framework. Vuforia has been used to ease the AR targets handling and to speed-up the development of the AR tools. Vuforia is an AR SDK specifically tailored for mobile platforms.

Figure 2. View through the AR Viewing tool, showing step index, instructional caption, annotation, and process step controls

The second major component of the AR Situation Awareness tool is the AR Authoring tool. The Authoring Tool is an application that enables the authoring of training scenarios, in an intuitive manner through the use of a node-based interface. In a sense, the authoring tool is the counterpart of the AR Viewing Tool, enabling the authoring of content that is fully compatible, and in fact designed for the tool in question. The nodes could be instantiated

on the grid, deleted and connected. Also, every node is able to store some information. Through the connection of nodes a scenario is specified, with scenario steps described by the sequence of nodes. The overall workflow of the AR Authoring Tool is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Scenario Creation Diagram for the AR Authoring Tool

The authoring tool has been developed in the Unity application. A snapshot of the tool development is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Unity's Environment

Through the use of the AR Authoring Tool, scenarios are determined through a node-based interface, where the user chains together nodes that represent the steps of the modeled process. The user is able to add media to the project, to make the steps more clear to the final user of the AR viewing tool. Those media contain images, videos and audio files, which can explain the specific step of the scenario more precisely and in better terms. In addition to media, the user of the authoring tool is able to add some 3D models to make the explanation more understandable. In the following subsections we lay out the details of the platform operation and outline user operation.

3 Example use cases

As an initial validation step, the developed Situational Awareness tool has been applied to realize two separate training scenarios, in the form of instructional interactive AR applications. The scenarios concern the maintenance of a drilling machine and the change of filament in a 3D printer.

3.1 Drilling Machine Maintenance

The drilling machine's mobile application gives the user a realistic and interactive way to be trained and update his knowledge of how to replace the drill from the machine.

The application has been developed on the basis of the Unity engine. Unity is a cross-platform development environment featuring fundamental 2D and 3D capabilities. Also, a Third party platform Vuforia has been used to ease the AR targets handling and to speed-up the development of the AR tools. Vuforia is an AR SDK specifically tailored for mobile platforms.

The application explains step by step how to replace the drill from the drilling machine. The drilling machine is a representative 3D model of the Alztronic by Alzmetall. In order for the user to be able to use this application needs to print a piece of paper with an image see Figure 5. With the usage of Vuforia platform, the mobile camera searches to recognize an image (see Figure 5) in order to present the 3D model on the surface of this image.

Figure 5. Tag used for registration

The application provides instructions and animations to explain to the user which actions to perform with safety in order to replace the drill. The whole process is constituted by thirteen steps. In the figures below are demonstrated some of these steps with their instructions.

The user can browse between these steps and get textual as well as visual information regarding the replacing process (see Figures 6, 7). The textual information provides instruction of each particular step and the visual information is an animation of the 3D models which demonstrate the action of the user.

Figure 6. View through the AR Viewer app during an instructional step

Figure 7. View through the AR Viewer app during an instructional step, which includes an annotation to demonstrate the action

The instructional steps are as follows:

1. Press the emergency button to ensure that the machine is off
2. Open the protection glass

3. Insert the drill bit
4. Close the protection glass
5. Grab the object and insert it under the drill
6. Open the fuse to unlock height adjustment
7. Adjust height with the top lever
8. Close the fuse to lock height adjustment
9. Wear the protection goggles
10. Open the cap of the emergency button
11. Turn the machine on by pressing the green button
12. Drill a hole into the object by pulling the drilling adjustment lever
13. Turn the machine off by pressing the red button

3.2 3D Printer Maintenance

The drilling machine's mobile application gives the user a realistic and interactive way to be trained and update his knowledge of how to replace the drill from the machine. The 3D Printer mobile application enables the user to train themselves on basic 3D printer operations through an intuitive, interactive step-by-step guide. As with the drilling machine application, the 3D printer application is developed in the Unity engine, using the third-party Vuforia platform to handle AR tags. The application includes a step by step guide that trains a simple 3D printer procedure, namely the change of the 3D print filament. This is a standard procedure that needs to be carried out on a daily basis in 3D printer operation. The procedure is optimized for a specific 3D printer model, the Makerbot Ultimaker.

Figure 8 View through the AR Viewer app with instructions caption and annotation of the step

The application provides instructions and animations to explain to the user which actions to perform with safety in order to replace the drill. The whole process is constituted by thirteen steps. In the figures below are demonstrated some of these steps with their instructions. Similarly to the drill application presented in the previous chapter, the user can here too browse between steps and get textual as well as visual information regarding the process. Thus, each step is presented with a prompt on the bottom of the screen, as well as a 3D model annotating the desired actions overlaid over the point of interest.

To initiate the instructional procedure, the user needs to point their phone to a specific tag shown in Figure 5, which enables the system to register the desktop machine coordinate frame. Following this action, the steps are initiated and the user may skip through them at their own pace.

Figure 9 Another view through the AR Viewer app, where the annotation is registered with the object of interest

The instructional steps for changing the 3d printer filament are as follows:

1. Have the new filament at hand, next to the printer for the procedure
2. Turn on the printer through the power switch on the back
3. Navigate to the menu Material > Change on the printer screen; the printer will heat up the nozzle which will take a few minutes. Once the nozzle is heated up, the printer will start retracting the filament
4. Locate the material feeder assembly at the back of the machine. Observe as the old filament is retracted. Once completely retracted, pull the filament out
5. Roll the old filament back to the spool and push its edge through one of the side holes in the spool. Place the filament back in the material storage cabinet
6. Inspect the new filament and ensure it has a clean edge. If necessary, cut off 1cm off the edge
7. Insert the new filament to the material feeder assembly on the rear of the machine, between the feeder gears
8. Press continue on the printer screen

A video recording of the scenario in question is available on Youtube, in the following link:

<https://youtu.be/eJhCrO91J2c>

4 Conclusions

One of the main goals of Ageing@Work seeks to improve the ageing worker's awareness when being on-site or in remote locations. The AR Training tools outlined in the present deliverable contribute to this goal, through improving worker training, knowledge sharing within the organization, and contributing to overall productivity. The proposed tools help workers improve their performance, by immersing them in a training scenario where the workers can visualize the process as a whole, prioritize their work, see what is important and what is not on their next step and see the way they should do their tasks in a safer way. By using different augmented reality tools, ageing workers can be reminded of their scheduled tasks or other relevant tasks, of the dangers on the working site and receive some information as guidelines streams with a visualized description of that tasks, for improving the way they implement them.

In addition, through the use of the AR authoring tool, senior workers having experience on certain tasks, have an intuitive tool at their disposal to generate training scenarios, therefore further contributing to knowledge sharing within the organization. Through the tool, the user can create a big variety of complex and non-complex scenario's that will help the final user to prioritize their work and notify them of the importance of every task and the way they should implement it as efficient as possible.

References

- [1] R. Azuma, "A Survey of Augmented Reality, Tele-operators and Virtual Environments," in *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 1997.
- [2] M. Cidota, S. Lukosch, D. Datcu and H. Lukosch, "Workspace Awareness in Collaborative AR using HMDs: A User Study Comparing Audio and Visual Notifications," in *Proceedings of the 7th Augmented Human International Conference*, Geneva, 2016.
- [3] H. Martínez, D. Skournetou, J. Hyppölä, S. Laukkanen and A. & Heikkilä, "Drivers and Bottlenecks in the Adoption of Augmented Reality Applications," *Journal of Multimedia Theory and Applications*, vol. 1, p. 27–44., 2014.
- [4] M. Lee and P. Morris, "Lifelong learning, income inequality and social mobility in Singapore," *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 286-312, 2016.